

Nutritional and Health Enhancing Properties of Whey

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INTRODUCTION

India is the world's largest producer of milk (Shivaje *et al.*, 2004). India's estimated milk production in the year ending March 1999, of 74 million ton, was 13% of the world's milk production. The world milk production was estimated at 612 million ton in 2004, the increase from 2003 being less than 3 million ton (IDF, 2004).

With increases in milk production in the country, surplus milk is available for conversion into value added products. The production of cheese, chhana and paneer – around 218 million ton annually (Alam *et al.*, 2001), generate large quantity of whey which is a rich source of nutrients.

In India about 80 % of total whey produced is obtained from chhana or paneer. It is estimated that more than 3 million ton of whey is produced annually, containing about 2 lakh ton of valuable milk nutrients (Devi *et al.*, 2004).

Consumer across the globe are now very health conscious. They are looking for certain ingredients in food which aid bodily function in addition to nutritional profile. Emerging research suggests that whey-derived bioactive components have antimicrobial and antiviral properties, enhance the immune defence, possess anti-oxidative activity, may help against cancer and cardiovascular diseases and enhance the physical performance or physical activity (Walzem, *et al.*, 2002; Harper 2000).

Whey protein has a high biological value compared to most other proteins. It has a high content of sulphur containing amino acids important for biosynthesis of glutathione, a tripeptide with antioxidant, anticarcinogenic and immune stimulating properties. It is also the highest natural source of branched amino acids, which may stimulate muscle protein synthesis (Brody, 2000; Shah, 2000; Arington, 2003).

TYPE AND COMPOSITION OF WHEY

Whey is the milk serum that is produced during the manufacture of paneer, chhana and shrikhand after separation of casein and fat during milk coagulation. Depending on the way in which casein is coagulated, i.e. by enzymatic rennet coagulation or by acid coagulation, whey can be divided into rennet whey and acid whey.

Acid Whey (Paneer Whey)

Acid whey is a milk serum obtained during an acid-coagulation process. The pH value of acid whey ranges from 5.1 or below (Zall, 1992), depending upon the type of acid used for precipitation (lactic acid or mineral acids). Acid whey contains less lactose and protein content than rennet whey but acid whey is a rich source of calcium and phosphorus as compared to cheese whey (Table 1).

Sweet Whey (Rennet Whey)

Rennet whey is milk serum obtained during enzymatic coagulation of casein (Zall 1992) and is basically free from calcium, therefore no calcium lactate can be formed with lactic acid. The TS, fat and protein content of rennet whey is more than acid whey and has a pH range of 5.9 – 6.6 (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Composition of Acid and Sweet Whey

Composition	Sweet Whey (Rennet Whey)	Acid Whey (Paneer Whey)
Solids, %	6.87	6.06
pH	6.4	5.6
Lactose, %	5.01	5.03
Protein, %	0.98	0.3
Fat, %	0.34	0.13
Ash %	0.54	0.6
Lactic Acid, %	0.14	0.21

Source: Durham *et al.*, (1997)

NUTRITIONAL PROPERTIES OF WHEY

Dairy whey is a yellow green liquid that results from transformation of milk into cheese, casein, paneer or other coagulated dairy products. The total solids content is only 62g/l. It includes protein, lactose, mineral matter and water-soluble vitamins.

Protein

Whey protein includes β -lactoglobulin (3.2 g/l), α -lactalbumin (1.2 g/l), bovine serum albumin (0.4 g/l), immunoglobulin (0.8g/l), lactoferrin (0.2 g/l) and lactoperoxidase (0.2g/l) Whey protein ranks high on the basis of higher protein efficiency ratio (PER – 3.6), biological value (BA – 104) and net protein utilization (NPU – 95) as compared to other proteins (Klhamrui *et al.*, 1998).

Specific Amino Acids

Whey proteins are rich source of both sulfur containing and branched chain amino acids as compared to major sources of protein (Table 2). The high content of sulphur-containing amino acids (cysteine and methionine) of whey protein enhances the immune function and the antioxidant properties. Whey proteins contain highest concentration of branched chain amino acids (L-iso leucine, L-leucine and L-valine); provide safe nutritional support for athletes and individuals seeking optimal lean muscle man. Tryptophan, which acts as building block for niacin, is present as higher amount of whey protein (Durham *et al.*, 1997).

Enzymes

The enzymes are mainly employed in the process of digestion and are of little nutritional significance. The important enzyme, which is present in the whey, is lactoperoxidase. Lactoperoxidase is an oxidoreductase that breaks down hydrogen peroxide. It is the enzyme that has anticarcinogenic activity apart from the immunoglobulins, bio-active peptide, and growth factors which stimulates cell growth. This component of whey is an enzyme with anti bacterial properties. Lactoperoxidase is used in various cosmetics and food preservatives. It is a food preservative.

Vitamins

Water-soluble vitamins in milk remain in the serum and are

TABLE 2. Amino Acid Profile of some Major Protein Sources

Essential Amino Acids	Protein Source (mg/g of protein)					
	Wheat	Rice	Soya	Egg	Casein	Whey Protein
Iso Lucine	14	15	21	28	46	55
Leucine	27	32	31	34	91	111
Lysine	11	15	26	29	77	88
Methionine	06	10	05	14	29	25
Phenylalanine	18	18	19	23	51	34
Threonine	12	15	16	21	43	72
Trptophan	05	05	05	05	12	30
Valine	18	25	24	29	57	52
Histidine	21	21	24	21	30	22

Source: Gopalan et al., (1996)

collected with the whey. The concentration of vitamin C is reduced during the processing and so, whey is not considered a significant source of vitamin C. Whey products will naturally fortify the thiamin, riboflavin, pantothenic acid, Vitamin B⁶ and Vitamin B¹² contents of the food. Vitamin A, D, E and K are separated with the milk fat that is entrapped in the curd and separated with the whey cream.

Minerals

Whey is a good source of certain essential minerals. These are presented in Table 3. As the pH of milk decreases during acid cheese production, more of the salts dissociate. This results in higher concentration of soluble calcium, magnesium, zinc and phosphorous in acid whey. Mineral concentration is reduced by electrodialysis and ultrafiltration.

TABLE 3. Essential Mineral Content of Acid and Sweet Whey

Minerals	Acid Whey	Sweet Whey
	Major Mineral, mg/100 g	
Calcium	42.8	36.5
Magnesium	9.0	6.5
Sodium	39.8	39.8
Potassium	153	153.0
Phosphorus	58.0	58.0
	Trace Mineral, µg/100g	
Zinc	234	11
Iron	106	89
Copper	6.8	3.5
Manganese	2.8	0.6

Source: Wong et al., (1978)

Lactose

Whey is a very good source of lactose. It comprises 77% of total solids corresponding to 48g/l in whey (Nielson 2003). It may also improve the absorption of calcium (Renner 1992). Lactose stimulates the growth of acid forming lactobacilli in the intestinal tract i.e. act as a probiotic substrate. Literature also suggested prophylactic effect of whey against tuberculosis and arthritis. Recent nutritional studies suggest that lactobacilli help in fighting intestinal disorders and that lactose could be used in dietary therapy for ailing infants.

BIOLOGICAL AND HEALTH ENHANCING PROPERTIES OF WHEY

The biological properties of whey and its components have both current and future potential in the nutrition and health of people and in preventing diseases (Zalzem, 2001). Findings from *invitro* studies, animal bioassays and limited human studies suggest the following beneficial bioactivities of whey.

Antimicrobial and Antiviral Activities

Whey contains immunoglobulins (Igs), lactoferrin and its

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peptide derivative lactoferricin, lactoperoxiadase, glycomacropeptide and sphingolipids. Whey derived sphingolipid, sphingosine and lysosphingolmyelin have antimicrobial activity. Lactoferrin and lactoferricin inhibit the microorganisms including gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria, yeast, fungi and parasitic protozoa. Lactoferrin inhibits the growth of some harmful food born pathogens such *E. Coli* and *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Antiviral activity has been described for several whey components including lactoferrin, lactoperoxidase, immunoglobulins and minor whey proteins. Lactoferrin has significant antiviral activity against human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) herpes virus and hepatitis C virus, among others. (Walzem, 2001).

Immuni Modulating Activity

Whey products and their components participate in host immunity (Harper, 2000) Lactoferrin can stimulate the growth of various cells of the immune defense system including lymphocytes, macrophages/monocytes, humoral immune response and antibody response. In human beings, increase immune responsiveness was demonstrated in patients given lactoferrin prior to thyroid surgery. The glutathione antioxidant system is a critical factor in the development of immune response by immune cell.

Cardiovascular Health

Whey peptides have shown an angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitory activity both *invitro* and in animal experiments. The overall effect of an ACE inhibitor is the control of high blood pressure through dilation of blood vessels and its effect on blood volume. While angiotensin I is an inactive hormone, antiotensin II is a molecule that directly constricts vascular smooth muscle, thereby increasing blood pressure (Saito *et al.*, 1997). Angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) converts the inactive angiotensin I into angiotensin II. Inhibition of ACE lowers blood pressure.

Anti-cancer Activity

Increasing evidence from cellular and animal models indicates that whey, whey protein and peptides, as well as other whey components help in fighting against cancer. In an in vitro study, whey protein isolate enhanced the effectiveness of an anticancer drug (Bounus, 1991). Whey containing diets have been shown to reduce intestinal, mammary and colon cancer.

Physical Performance

Whey contains easily digestible high quality proteins that provide additional energy. Whey proteins contain high level of branched chain amino acids (leucine, isoleucine and valine). Since the body's demand for these amino acids increases during exercise, athletes who want to preserve muscle mass may benefit by increasing their consumption. It is a good source of sulphur containing amino acids (cystene and methionine) to maintain antioxidant level in body (Harper 2000).

Other Health Benefits

Some whey components may protect against tooth tissue demineralization. A whey protein in cow's milk with a high content of tryptophan improved cognitive performance in stress-vulnerable individuals.

CURRENT STATUS OF WHEY UTILIZATION

Whey has been recognized as a source of diverse biological active components with unique physiological opportunities for the food industry to develop functional foods, or foods that have potential health benefits beyond their nutrient content. Because of high transportation costs and susceptibility to deterioration during storage, fresh pasteurized liquid whey is rarely used as such for foods, but rather is concentrated by evaporation, reverse osmosis or ultrafiltration to condensed products or maximally concentrated by drying. Whey powder, whey protein concentrates, whey protein isolates, reduced lactose whey and demineralized whey are produced from

whey.

In addition, whey protein isolates can be heated with acid or treated with proteolytic enzymes to develop small fractions of proteins, i.e. bioactive amino acids and peptides from whey. Utilization of whey/whey solids started with animal feed production. Now it has entered into human food chain in one or other forms as whey components are used in bakery, confectionary, beverage, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry.

Current consumer preference regarding food intake are for more protein and fiber but with continued decrease in fat. Certainly whey and whey ingredients can be used as a fat replacer/reducer in variety of products, such as meats, soups, sauces, salad dressing, baked goods and more. They can also be used as fortifying ingredients in beverage and snack bars. WPC have been allocated as an alternative protein source in a lunch programme in USA (Berry 2002). Therefore, whey products are recognized for their high nutritional value and versatile functional properties in a multitude food products.

CONCLUSION

Whey is an important dairy by-product, which is highly nutritious and having many disease preventing properties. It is a source of high value protein, specific amino acid (sulphur containing and branched chain amino acid), water soluble vitamins except vitamin C, lactoperoxidase enzyme and essential minerals. Whey also contains antimicrobial, antiviral and immune modulating activities. It is useful for patients of high blood pressure. Whey containing diet reduces the intestinal, mammary and colon cancers. For the athletes whey is useful for physical performance.

REFERENCE

- Alam, T., venugopal, A. and Kanawjia, S.K. 2001. Status of dairy Industry in India. *Beverage and Food World*. 28 (10): 37-40.
- Arlington, V.A. 2003. U.S. Dairy Export Council. U.S. Dairy Council, Reference Mannual for U.S. Whey and Lactose Product.
- Berry, D. 2002. Whey proteins role. *J. Dairy Food.*, 103(10): 38-46.
- Bounous, G. 1991. whey proteins in cancer prevention. *Cancer Lett.*, 57:91-94.
- Bulletin of IDF 2004. *The World Dairy Situation*. Pp 391.
- Devi, S., Banumathi, P. and Jothi, M. 2004. Studies on development and evaluation of whey based fruit beverage. *Beverage and Food World*. 31 (11):44-45.
- Durham, R.J., Hourigan, J.A., Singh, R.W. and Johnsen, R.L. 1997. Whey fractionation: Wheying up consequences. *Food Australia*. 49 (10):460-465.
- Gopalan, G., Ramasastri, B.V. and Balasubranian, S.C. 1996. Nutritive value of Indian foods. National Institute of Nutrition, Hyderabad, p.156.
- Harper, W.J. 2000. Biological properties of whey components: A review. Cited: www.dpi.org
- Khamrui, K and Rajorhia, G.S. 1998. Making profits from whey. *Indian Dairyman*, 0 (6):13-18
- Nielsen, W.K. 2003. Whey processing. *Market Development. Dairy Industrial Int.*, 68(12):31-33.
- Renner, E. 1992. Nutritional aspects. In: *Lactose and whey processing*. J. Zadow (Ed.). Elsevier Applied Science, London and New York. P. 146-371.
- Saito, T., Abukabar, A., Itoh, T., Arai, I. And Aimar, M.V. 1997. Development of new type of fermented cheese whey beverage with inhibitory effect against angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE). *Tohok. J. Agri. Res.*, 48 (11-12):15-23. Cited: CAB Abstracts, 1997-98, 6.
- Shivajie, A., Kasture, M., Pandharik, M. and Mathankar, M. 2004. Milk production in India. *Current Science*, 86 (10):1346.
- Walzem, R.L. 2002. Health enhancing properties of whey proteins and whey fractions. *Applications Monograph. Nutritional and Beverage. U.S. Dairy Export Council*.
- Wong, N.P., La Croix, D.E. and McDonough, F.E. 1978. Minerals in whey and whey fraction. *J. Dairy Sci.* 61, 1700-1703
- Zall, R.R. 1992. Sources and composition of whey on permeate. In : *Whey and Lactose processing*. Edited by J.G Zadow. Elsewier Appl. Sci., London. Pp. 367-408